

**STUDYING THE FEATURES OF PHYSICAL TRAINING OF ATHLETES IN
SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING****Usmanov Bahadir Habibullaevich****Namangan State University****Associate Professor of the Department of Physical Culture****e-mail: usmanovbahodir728@gmail.com**

Annotation: Running is not only one of the main means of physical training and a healthy lifestyle, but also the most accessible form of physical education and multi-purpose sports activities. Running short distances gradually increases the vital capacity of the lungs, taking in more air and enriching the blood with oxygen. The heart rate increases and active blood circulation occurs in the body, thereby strengthening health, ensuring reliable psychological stability and developing speed to improve sportsmanship.

Keywords: running, physical qualities, speed, speed, sport.

**ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ
ЛЕГКОАТЛЕТОВ В БЕГЕ НА КОРОТКИЕ ДИСТАНЦИИ****Усманов Баходир Хабибуллаевич****Наманганский Государственный Университет****доцента кафедры Физической культуры****e-mail: usmanovbahodir728@gmail.com**

Аннотация: Бег не только является одним из главных средств физической подготовки, здорового образа жизни, но и самым доступным видом физкультурных и спортивных занятий многоцелевого назначения. Бег на короткие дистанции постепенно способствует увеличению жизненной ёмкости лёгких, набирая больше воздуха и обогащая кислородом кровь. Повышается сердцебиение и происходит активное кровообращение в организме, этим самым укрепляет здоровье, обеспечивает надёжную психологическую устойчивость и развивает быстроту для совершенствования спортивного мастерства.

Ключевые слова: бег, физические качества, быстрота, скорость, спорт.

Features of physical fitness of athletes in short distance running.

Short or sprint distance running includes running 60, 100, 200, and 400 m. The Olympic program includes 100, 200, and 400 m distances and 4 X 100 and 4 X 400 m relay races. Schoolchildren compete at distances from 30 to 400 m, depending on their age.

Sprinting is characterized by high speed (up to 11.0-11.5 m/s), great power, and movement

speed.

Running fast has been known since ancient times. At the Olympic Games in ancient Greece, athletes competed in the 1st and 2nd stadia races, which correspond to our 100m and 200m races.

Currently, sprint running has become an indispensable program for any athletics competition, including the Olympic Games. For a long time, American athletes were the strongest in short-distance running.

Achieving high results in short-distance running is impossible without sufficiently versatile and special physical training, especially without sufficiently high development of speed, power, and speed-power qualities, as well as coordination abilities.

According to the recently adopted section, there are three stages in the long-term training of young short-distance runners: the pre-training stage (10-12-year-old children); the stage of elementary sports specialization (13-15-year-old teenagers); the stage of intensive sports training (16-17-year-old boys and girls).

During the initial training of young sprinters, the following tasks are solved: strengthening health and all-around physical development; teaching the basics of the technique of performing large-scale general developmental exercises; and developing a stable interest in regular sports, in particular athletics.

The main means of education: general developmental exercises; acrobatic elements (flips, standing, turns, etc.); exercises on gymnastic equipment (lifting, pulling, hanging, stopping, leaning, swinging, etc.); various jumping exercises and jumps; various shooting and throwing exercises; a wide range of speed-strength exercises; running in a straight line (uphill, downhill) at different speeds for segments of 20-60 m; various action games.

The main methods of performing exercises: are game, repetition, uniform, circle, and control.

At the initial training stage, it is necessary to take into account the general methodological rules specific to the training of young sprinters.

Exercises that mainly develop movement speed require a lot of nervous tension. Therefore, a set of speed exercises should be introduced at the beginning of training, immediately after warming up (that is when the level of excitation of the central nervous system is optimal). After a set of speed-developing exercises, it is advisable to include movement games that strengthen this quality in training.

In the second half of the workout, it is recommended to introduce strength-building

exercises, because by this time the functional capabilities of the body's support systems - breathing, blood circulation, etc. - are most fully manifested. As in the previous case, strength training sets are supported by action games with elements of power struggle.

The main tasks of training at the stage of initial sports specialization are: strengthening health and all-round physical development; step-by-step transition to targeted training in the chosen form of athletics; training techniques for various types of athletics exercises and multi-level training.

The main means of training at this stage are: running at different speeds in segments of 200-300 m; action games and game exercises; general development exercises; acrobatic elements (somersaults, flips, etc.) gymnastic exercises on equipment, various jumping and jumping exercises; various shooting and throwing exercises; special training exercises for sprints and hurdles.

All these exercises are carried out using game, repetitive, uniform, rotational, controlled, and competitive teaching methods.

Although general physical training remains the main goal of the training at this stage, special preparatory exercises are given a more important place. This ensures the unity of general and special physical training of young short-distance runners.

At the stage of perfect training, the following main tasks are solved: strengthening health and all-round physical development; improving speed-power training, taking into account specialization in sprint running; increasing the speed of movement; training and improvement of athletics techniques; gradually increasing the volume and intensity of training and competition loads.

Basic tools: general developmental exercises, special preparatory exercises; various jumping and jumping exercises; various shooting and throwing exercises; a set of special running exercises, exercises with weights (barbell, weights, dumbbells, exercise balls, etc.); running at different speeds over distances of 20-400 m; action and sports games; long slow running (cross country) up to 30-40 minutes.

Short-distance running is included in the standards of "Alpomish" and "Barchina" complexes.

Special training for sprinters at high school age plays an important role. At this stage, the approximate ratio of general and special training should be 45 and 55%, respectively.

At all stages of training sprinters, the level of general physical fitness is increased mainly with the help of various gymnastic exercises without equipment and with equipment. In this

case, the main focus should be on the development of muscles and muscle groups that carry the main load in short-distance running: flexors and extensors of the leg, thigh, and torso.

General endurance is the basis of a sprinter's performance. Based on it, other physical qualities develop more successfully. It is desirable to develop general endurance through uniform running at a low speed on the ground (cross-country skiing), as well as through various active sports games and other sports.

Strength is important for young sprinters. These qualities are developed in the process of both general physical and special training. At present, in the practice of sports training, it is said that, finally, based on the characteristics of sprint running, it is necessary to develop the strength qualities of athletes. In other words, the power qualities of short-distance runners are improved more effectively during the performance of speed-strength exercises: various jumping and jumping exercises, running in difficult conditions, throwing balls of different weights from different starting positions, gymnastics, and acrobatic exercises.

In all cases, it should be remembered that strength training should be replaced by stretching and relaxation exercises.

Speed is the key quality that determines success in sprinting. At the same time, it is more difficult to develop speed during training than other qualities, because the scope of individual improvement of this quality is determined genetically. It was found that if the speed of the sprinter's movements is mainly developed through short sprints at approximately maximum and maximum speed, this method soon becomes ineffective and something called a speed barrier occurs. To develop speed, you need a variety of jumping and throwing exercises performed for a long time and at maximum speed, imitating individual minutes of sprinting, as well as various movement and sports games, including fast short-term running, jumping, and throwing. With increasing age, experience of regular training, and increasing sports skills, the proportion of special means for developing movement speed should increase - various runs at maximum and maximum speed.

Special endurance is manifested in the sprinter's ability to maintain a high running speed throughout the distance. This quality is developed by running distances of 100-300 m at approximately maximum and maximum speed. Adequate rest between runs is necessary to maintain the ability to complete each repetition at a certain speed. An effective means of developing and improving the special endurance of short-distance runners is variable and interval running, as well as the game of running on difficult terrain ("Fartlek").

Often, when athletes of equal strength compete, success is accompanied by whoever has

better mental and willpower preparation. Regardless of the weather and other conditions, regular and strict execution of training plans develops the athlete's will to the perfect degree. Regular participation in competitions teaches athletes to suppress excessive anxiety and cope with feelings of uncertainty when competing against strong opponents.

Planning lessons. In recent years, since athletics competitions are held almost all year round, the step-by-step planning of the training process has also changed significantly.

The training period (November - April) is usually divided into three interconnected stages: autumn-winter training (November - January), winter competition (February - March), and spring training (March - April).

In the training of short-distance runners who have achieved results at the level of III-II categories, in the preparation stage for the autumn-winter season, first of all, it is necessary to improve running technique, increase general physical fitness, increase and improve general endurance. As a rule, sprinters of the third category train 3-4 times a week, 1.5-2 hours each, alternately in the hall (arena) and outdoors.

The goal of the winter competition stage is to further increase the level of physical fitness achieved through regular participation in training and control evaluations.

In the spring preparation stage, the level of general and speed-strength training increases, and special endurance improves. At this time, the amount of general physical training gradually decreases, and the amount of special training means increases. The speed of running the segments from a low start gradually increases, which allows you to improve the speed and technique of the start and start acceleration.

The main tasks of the summer competition period are to increase speed, special endurance, running technique, maintain general physical fitness at the achieved level, and finally, to directly prepare for the main competitions, to achieve the highest results. During this period, the volume of educational tools is slightly reduced, and their intensity increases. Junior sprinters, even during the summer competition season, should pay close attention to general conditioning and weight training, while continuing to improve their cross-country training.

The growth of the sport in athletics and in particular the results of sprinting depends to a large extent on the effective distribution of training and competitive loads at different levels. In recent studies, one of the rational methods of organizing the training load in the annual cycle is the approach of concentration, the concentration of training loads of different main areas at certain stages. This form of organization of the training process imposes new requirements on the construction of a mesocycle, where it is necessary to rationally distribute the training load

between microcycles, optimally combining these microcycles into a single system, taking into account the skills of athletes.

By the established periodicity of the annual cycle, there are two six-month cycles in the training of sprinters: the first and the second. In this regard, the planning of training loads is carried out according to mesocycles and periods of training.

Taking into account the above, the following is necessary to effectively organize the training of short-distance runners in the annual cycle:

- to determine the actual values of the annual training volume
- loading performed by highly qualified sprinters and qualified sprinters;
- to study the distribution of volumes of educational loads in different main directions in medium and small training cycles.

The analysis of training loads made it possible to obtain average values of the volume of the main training equipment per year for track and field athletes. The given information refers to the stage of deep specialization (ages 16-18) and improvement of sports (ages 19 and older).

To analyze the main trends in the distribution of loads, the partial volumes of the main training facilities were calculated as a percentage of the total annual volume in monthly cycles, 100%.

As the athletes' skill increases, the volume of the training load increases significantly ($P = 0.05$) for all the considered training tools. It should be noted that skilled athletes perform 25-27% less running load than highly skilled sprinters.

In recent years, the practical experience of training high-class athletes shows that high indicators of total workload are one of the factors that ensure the achievement of high sports results. But an important condition for improving the technical skills of athletes and increasing their special physical fitness is to ensure the optimal balance of the work of different main directions.

Based on modern requirements, trainings are organized in every way in all periods of the annual cycle, which ensures the improvement of the technical skills of the athletes and the improvement of their special physical fitness. However, because at each stage of the annual cycle in training, the focus is on solving specific training problems, a characteristic feature of the dynamics of loads of qualified sprinters is the uneven distribution of partial volumes of the main training tools by stages.

This distribution of the volume of tools in different directions allows us to talk about the predominance of the load in a certain direction in each training mesocycle.

The characteristics of the distribution of training loads in monthly cycles for short-distance runners look like this:

1. Differences between skilled sprinters and highly skilled sprinters in the distribution of alactic-anaerobic running load (running up to 80 m at a speed of 100-96%) are insignificant. The maximum volume of this load occurred in January (15.7 and 16.4% of annual volume per month) and May (19.4 and 20.1%, respectively) among skilled and highly skilled runners. No high-intensity running is planned during the transition period (October).

2. Anaerobic-glycolytic running load (running at a speed of 100-91% over 100-300 m segments) is mainly carried out in the second six-month cycle. The maximum load is planned for April (20 and 18.1%) and May (24.1-24.8% of the annual volume).

3. Sprinters perform a large amount of anaerobic-aerobic running load (running at 90-81% speed for 100-300 m) during the general preparation stages in November - January and April.

4. Aerobic running (running at less than 80% speed over 300 m) is performed in large quantities in November (21.5 and 21.2%, respectively) and April (about 14%).

5. Jumping exercises (speed-power direction) are used in significant volumes in the stages of general training and special training. In the first six-month cycle, the main volume of jumping exercises performed by qualified and highly qualified sprinters falls in November-January; in the second cycle, large-scale jumping exercises are performed in March and April.

6. Weight-bearing exercises are used in the first six-month cycle in large quantities in November (about 19%) and December (22.7 and 22.6%) by skilled sprinters and highly skilled runners, respectively. Thus, in each major training cycle, the following will always prevail:

- aerobic loads and general physical education means; mixed loads and special strength (speed-strength) training tools;

- anaerobic lactic and glycolytic loads. In particular, the analysis of the literature on the problem of adaptation to physical activity (Mishchenko B.C., 1990, Matveev L.P., 1991) shows that such a distribution of the training load creates favorable conditions for the implementation of training tasks at each subsequent stage. Create a database.

The analysis of training and training plans and diaries of sprinters made it possible to identify general trends in the organization of loads and to consider the scheme of distribution of training tools for small (weekly) training cycles. Loading volumes are recorded depending on the size and degree of impact on the athlete: small, medium, and large volumes.

Organization of the load in the middle periods of the annual cycle implies the following.

Autumn-winter general preparation stage. In the prevailing opinions about the regularities

of the periodization of the training process, the main direction of the training in the general preparation stage is to create, expand, and improve the conditions that form the sports form.

At this stage, athletes solve the problems of increasing speed-power and general physical fitness. For highly skilled runners, the duration of the stage is up to eight weeks. The optimal duration of the training load of the relevant main direction is determined, first of all, by the characteristics of the body's adaptation to various training effects. Predominant use of aerobic running loads has been shown to increase aerobic performance within 2-3 months. A reasonable duration of aerobic running for short-distance runners is 4-8 weeks. The analysis showed significant changes in the dynamics of stage loads, but the following load distribution options were most often used.

Special preparation stage for autumn-winter. Training at this stage is aimed at the immediate development of sports form. The main task is to improve the athlete's speed and technical skills. The duration of the stage for highly skilled runners is 5-6 weeks. At this stage, the percentage of special training increases, which is expressed in the predominance of anaerobic running load. Strength training is maintained by performing speed-strength exercises performed in medium and small volumes in each microcycle. The working loads of the lactic-anaerobic and anaerobic-glycolytic directions are "diluted" in time. The reason for this is that speed endurance work leads to a significant accumulation of lactic acid in the body, requires a strain on energy resources, and ultimately enters into a competitive relationship with the speed program. While shock microcycles, where mainly glycolytic exercises are performed, are located at the beginning and the end of the phase, the maximum volume of alactic-anaerobic load occurs in the middle of the phase (3-4 weeks) by the end of the phase.

At the same time, athletes who plan to perform only short sprint distances in the winter season perform a very small amount of anaerobic-glycolytic load.

The period of winter competitions. The main tasks of this period are to maintain and further increase the level of special training and use it more fully in competitions. Physical training takes the form of direct functional preparation for extreme competitive stress. The analysis of best practices for building a training process for highly qualified sprinters showed that the period of winter competitions, as a rule, consists of 4-6 microcycles. The organization of special physical training during the competition is carried out by the calendar of the main competitions.

Spring-summer general training stage. From this mesocycle, runners begin the second major cycle of training for summer races. The duration of the spring-summer general training

phase is about six weeks. Much attention is paid to increasing the level of speed-strength fitness and the functional capabilities of the body. Jumping exercises with weights and the volume of exercises increases regularly or spasmodically. Impact microcycles with large speed-power tools are usually located in the middle or at the end of the stage. After the microcycle shock, the size of the speed-power load, as a rule, decreases to a small load value.

Mixed (aerobic-anaerobic) loading prevails in the spring-summer general training phase. Compared to the winter general training phase, the amount of aerobic load is significantly reduced (as in the autumn-winter cycle). The dynamics of the working load in the aerobic-anaerobic (mixed) direction repeats the load distribution curve of a speed-power nature with a large load in the middle or at the end of the stage; Aerobic work is done on a large scale, usually at the beginning of the mesocycle. Targeted improvement of speed skills begins approximately in the middle of the mesocycle.

Spring-summer special training stage. In preparation for the summer race season, elite runners plan this stage for up to six weeks. In the course of the training, the tasks of improving the starting technique, starting acceleration (acceleration) and distance running, increasing the maximum running speed, and improving the indicators of speed endurance are solved. An anaerobic workload is preferred. Running at a speed of 100-96% up to 80 m is done in large volumes in the middle or at the end of the phase.

A large anaerobic-glycolytic load is usually carried out at the beginning and the end of a special training period. Work on increasing speed is carried out in maintenance mode, large power-oriented loads, as a rule, are not used.

Summer competition period. During the entire period, the main tasks of the educational process are to create the most favorable conditions for achieving high sports results in the mastered sport. The entire training is aimed at improving sprinting skills - maximum running speed and special endurance.

The duration of summer competitions for highly skilled sprinters is 12-15 weeks. In training, the greatest preference is given to loads of alactic-anaerobic and glycolytic nature. Speed power loads are done in small amounts throughout the competition.

Complex of physical training of athletes in short distance running.

The presented data confirm the existence of concentration of certain loads in different mesocycles of year-round training in the training of highly skilled short-distance runners. This situation makes it possible to divide training loads into groups and programs according to the nature of their effect on the body, bioenergy during exercise, and the pedagogical effect of

exercise. Basic training programs for highly skilled sprinters:

Program 1 - aerobic exercises. Cross-country running up to 30 minutes. Running 400 m at a speed below 80% (heart rate - 120-130 beats/min).

Used:

- in the stage of general preparation - 1-2 times a week;
- during the special training phase - once a week;
- during the competition - 1 time per week (up to 15 minutes or as a means of recovery after the competition).

Program 2 - aerobic-anaerobic exercises. Running 100-300 m at 90-81% speed.

Used:

- in the stage of general preparation - up to 3-4 times a week;
- in the stage of special preparation - 2-3 times a week;
- during the competition - 1-2 times a week.

Program 3 - anaerobic-glycolytic exercises. Running 100-300 m at a speed of 100-91%.

Used:

- in the stage of general preparation - 1-2 times a week;
- in the stage of special training - up to 2 times a week;
- during the selection period - 1 time per week.

Program 4 - alactic-anaerobic exercises. Run up to 80m at 100-96% speed.

Used:

- in the stage of general preparation - 1-2 times a week;
- in the stage of special preparation - 2-3 times a week;
- during the competition - 2-3 times a week (including participation in competitions).

Program 5: SSP - speed-strength training (jumping exercises and exercises with weights).

It should be noted here that in the studied literature (Khomeikov J.C., 1987; Ozolin N., Voronkin V.I., Primakov Yu.N., 1989, etc.) the separation of speed-strength exercises is not considered. independent program. However, to visually show the entire training load of sprinters, we decided to analyze these training sessions of track and field athletes and separate them into a separate program.

Used:

- in the stage of general preparation - 2 times a week;
- in the stage of special preparation - 2-3 times a week;
- during the competition - 1-2 times a week.

To effectively build a training microcycle, it is necessary to take into account the impact of loads of different sizes and directions on the athlete, as well as the dynamics and duration of recovery processes after them. Information about the cumulative effect of various loads to enhance the recovery processes after great physical stress is less important. When planning two or three classes with different loads per day, it is necessary to know the fluctuations of special indicators during the day and the mechanisms that cause them.

Alternating loads and rest in a microcycle can lead to three types of reactions:

- the first, is clear educational effect with the maximum growth of training;
- secondly, insignificant educational effect or its complete absence;
- Third, overwork of the athlete.

The first type of reaction is typical for all cases in which the microcycle contains an optimal number of activities with large and significant loads, which are rationally exchanged with each other and with less loaded activities. If the microcycle includes a small number of exercises with a load that can serve as a stimulus for increasing physical activity, the second type of reaction occurs. Finally, the abuse of heavy loads or the illogicality of replacing them can cause the athlete to overwork, that is, it can cause the third type of reaction.

Based on the obtained data, the training of a sprinter can be considered as the implementation of certain training programs. In addition, each program in the weekly microcycle can be performed in large, medium, and small volumes.

REFERENCES

1. Анищенко В.С. Физическая культура: Методико-практические занятия для студентов: Учеб. пособие. - М.: Изд-во РУДНД999
2. Выдрин В.М., Зыков Б.К., Лотоненко А.В. Физическая культура студентов вузов. М.: Финансы и статистика, 1993.
3. Готовцев П.И., Дубровский В.Л. Самоконтроль при занятиях физической культурой. М.: Физкультура и спорт, 1991.
4. Залесский М., Рейзер Л. Путешествие в страну бега.- М.: Физкультура и спорт, 1987.
5. Иванов Г.Д. Физическое воспитание. Учебник. Алматы: РИК, 2005.
6. Малков Е.А. Подружись с королевой спорта. - 2-е изд. - М.: Просвещение, 1991.
7. Матвеев Л.П. Теория и методика физической культуры. - М.: ФиС, 2001
8. Теория спорта/ Под ред.Платонова В.Н.: Киев: Высшая школа, 1987

9. Физическая культура (курс лекций): Учебное пособие/Под общ. ред. Волковой Л.М., Половникова П.В.,СПб, 1998.-153 с.
10. Физическая культура студента. Учебник для студентов вузов. /Под общ. ред. В.И. Ильинича. - М.:Гардарики, 2003

